

Drivers, Dynamics, and Carbon Consequences of Forest Change in Myanmar: A Remote Sensing-Based Review

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Abstract

Tropical forests play a critical role in global carbon cycling and climate-change mitigation, yet they continue to experience rapid degradation in many developing countries due to socioeconomic pressures, climate variability, and weak governance. Advances in satellite remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) have significantly enhanced the ability to monitor forest-cover dynamics and associated carbon stock changes in data-limited regions. This review synthesizes recent literature on remote sensing-based assessments of land-use and land-cover (LULC) change and forest carbon dynamics in Myanmar, with particular emphasis on evidence from the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest in the Bago Region between 2017 and 2024. Drawing on studies employing Sentinel-2 imagery, post-classification change detection, and IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting approaches, the review highlights dominant deforestation and degradation pathways, carbon-emission hotspots, and the limited extent of forest regeneration. Socioeconomic drivers, hydroclimatic variability, and policy and governance constraints are critically examined to contextualize observed patterns. The review highlights the importance of integrating high-resolution Earth observation data with IPCC-compliant methodologies to support REDD+ implementation, enhance national forest monitoring systems, and inform sustainable forest management and climate policy in Myanmar and similar tropical forest landscapes.

Keywords: *Land-use and land-cover change, forest carbon dynamics, Sentinel-2, IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting, REDD+, Myanmar.*

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Introduction

Deforestation and forest degradation remain among the most significant drivers of global environmental change, contributing substantially to greenhouse gas emissions and biodiversity loss. Land-use and land-cover (LULC) change alters ecosystem structure and function, undermining the capacity of forests to act as long-term carbon sinks and, in many cases, transforming them into net sources of atmospheric carbon dioxide. Tropical forests are especially important in this context, as they store disproportionately large amounts of above- and below-ground biomass carbon while being highly vulnerable to anthropogenic disturbance (Fan et al., 2008)

Myanmar represents a critical case within Southeast Asia, having experienced sustained forest loss over recent decades due to agricultural expansion, fuelwood extraction, infrastructure development, and

governance challenges. National-scale analyses indicate that deforestation rates remained high during the early 2000s and have continued to exert pressure on forest carbon stocks (Liu et al., 2016). Within the country, the Bago Mountain Range has been identified as a hotspot of forest degradation, including within designated protected areas such as reserved forests (Kyaw, 2018)

In response to these challenges, remote sensing and GIS have become indispensable tools for forest monitoring. The increasing availability of high-resolution satellite data, particularly from the Sentinel-2 mission, has enabled more detailed and temporally consistent assessments of LULC dynamics and associated carbon-stock changes. At the same time, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Tier-1 framework provides a standardized and policy-relevant approach for estimating forest biomass and carbon emissions in data-scarce environments.

This review paper synthesizes current evidence on remote sensing-based assessments of forest-cover change and carbon dynamics in Myanmar, with a particular focus on findings from the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest between 2017 and 2024. By consolidating methodological approaches, key results, and identified drivers, the review aims to highlight best practices, knowledge gaps, and implications for forest governance, REDD+ implementation, and climate-change mitigation.

Study Area Context: Forest Change in Bago Region

The Bago Region, located in central Myanmar, encompasses ecologically important forest landscapes within the Bago Yoma Mountain range. The Shwe Laung Reserved Forest, situated in Kyauktaga Township, covers approximately 19,000 ha and supports mixed deciduous and evergreen forest types shaped by a tropical monsoon climate (Win et al., 2025) (Fig.1). Despite its legal protection status, the reserve has been subject to increasing pressure from agricultural encroachment, fuelwood collection, small-scale logging, and settlement expansion (Kyaw, 2018).

Previous studies in the Bago Region have documented substantial reductions in forest cover alongside an expansion of degraded forest, rangeland, and flooded vegetation. These changes reflect both anthropogenic drivers and environmental variability, including rainfall fluctuations and flooding in low-lying areas. As such, the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest provides a representative case for examining the interaction between land-use dynamics, forest degradation, and carbon emissions in protected tropical landscapes (Liang et al., 2025).

Assessments (EIA) and rehabilitation plans, they lack explicit standards for soil quality or contamination thresholds. Furthermore, the absence of continuous monitoring mechanisms and dedicated soil protection legislation constrains effective enforcement (Mulenga, 2022; Wambwa et al., 2023).

Figure 1. GIS location of Shwe Laung Reserved Forest in Bago Region, Myanmar

Remote Sensing Approaches to LULC and Forest Carbon Assessment

Satellite Data and LULC Classification

Recent advances in satellite remote sensing, particularly the availability of Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance imagery, have substantially enhanced the capacity to monitor land-use and land-cover (LULC) dynamics in tropical forest landscapes (Drusch et al., 2012; Immitzer et al., 2016). Sentinel-2 provides a spatial resolution of up to 10 m, a high temporal revisit frequency, and atmospherically corrected reflectance products, making it especially suitable for detecting fine-scale land-cover changes in heterogeneous and data-limited environments (Pham et al., 2020; Karra et al., 2021). As a result, Sentinel-2 has become a widely adopted data source for analysing forest change and supporting land-use decision-making in developing countries (Liang et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025).

LULC classification derived from Sentinel-2 imagery plays a central role in sustainable forest resource management by enabling consistent multi-temporal assessment of forest persistence, degradation, and regeneration (Lu et al., 2004; Zewdie & Csaplovics, 2014). In protected forest landscapes such as the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest in the Bago Region of Myanmar, Sentinel-2–based classifications have proven effective in detecting not only abrupt deforestation but also more gradual degradation pathways, including transitions from forest to rangeland or flooded vegetation (Hansen et al., 2016; Naing Tun et al., 2021). The ability to capture these subtle changes is critical for early intervention, targeted enforcement, and prioritisation of restoration and assisted natural regeneration efforts (Kyaw, 2018; Toda et al., 2023).

Beyond forest conservation, Sentinel-2–based LULC analysis also supports sustainable urban and regional planning, particularly at forest–settlement interfaces experiencing rapid land transformation (Hansen et al., 2013; Robertson & Bakimchandra, 2024). Mapping built-up areas, cropland expansion, and forest margins allows planners to monitor encroachment into protected areas and to identify zones where development pressures intersect with conservation priorities (Ramanamurthy & Vijayasradhi, 2021). In monsoon-dominated regions, the ability of Sentinel-2 imagery to discriminate flooded vegetation and surface water further supports climate-resilient planning by identifying flood-prone areas unsuitable for permanent infrastructure and by highlighting wetlands that provide essential ecosystem services, including flood regulation (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014; Leung et al., 2024).

From a policy and governance perspective, the free availability and global coverage of Sentinel-2 Level-2A imagery make it particularly valuable for strengthening land-use planning and forest governance in developing countries (Karra et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2025). When integrated within GIS-based decision-support systems, Sentinel-2–derived LULC classifications enhance transparency, repeatability, and institutional coordination across forestry, environmental, and urban planning agencies (Gitima et al., 2025). Overall, the growing body of evidence demonstrates that Sentinel-2–based LULC classification serves as a critical bridge between Earth observation science and practical land-use governance, supporting integrated and climate-smart approaches to forest management and urban development in tropical regions (Angelsen et al., 2018).

Table 1. Remote Sensing Data Sources and Characteristics

Year	Source imagery	Cell Size	Type	Attribution
2017	Sentinel-2 L2A	10-meters	Thematic	Esri, Impact Observatory
2024	Sentinel-2 L2A	10-meters		

IPCC Tier-1 Carbon Accounting Framework

In data-limited contexts such as Myanmar, the IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting framework offers a pragmatic and transparent approach for estimating forest carbon stocks and emissions (IPCC, 2006;

Baasansuren et al., 2019). The Tier-1 approach relies on default above-ground biomass (AGB) coefficients stratified by ecological zone and land-cover class, enabling harmonised and comparable carbon assessments across regions and time periods (Hunka et al., 2024).

Studies reviewed here commonly apply a stock-difference approach, whereby net changes in forest biomass carbon are calculated as the balance between gains from forest regeneration and losses resulting from deforestation and forest degradation (Berhanu et al., 2023; Legesse et al., 2024). By integrating LULC transition matrices derived from Sentinel-2 classifications with IPCC Tier-1 AGB coefficients and standard carbon conversion factors, researchers are able to quantify carbon emissions and removals associated with observed land-cover changes in a consistent and policy-relevant manner (Gagula et al., 2025; Gao et al., 2025).

Although Tier-1 estimates carry higher uncertainty compared with higher-tier, field-calibrated approaches, their compatibility with satellite-based LULC analysis makes them particularly valuable for large-area assessments, REDD+ monitoring, and national greenhouse gas reporting in countries with limited forest inventory data (Angelsen et al., 2018; Hunka et al., 2024). When combined with high-resolution Sentinel-2 imagery, the Tier-1 framework provides a robust and scalable foundation for assessing forest carbon dynamics and informing climate-change mitigation and sustainable forest management strategies.

Key Findings on LULC Change and Carbon Dynamics (2017-2024)

Forest Persistence, Loss, and Regeneration

Evidence from Sentinel-2–based analyses indicates that a substantial proportion of forest cover in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest remained stable between 2017 and 2024. However, this overall persistence masks significant localized degradation. The dominant forest-loss pathways involved conversion from forest to flooded vegetation and rangeland, reflecting hydrological change, clearing, and gradual biomass depletion rather than abrupt deforestation alone (See Figure 2).

Forest regeneration was observed primarily through the conversion of rangeland back to tree cover, with only minor contributions from cropland, bare ground, and flooded vegetation. While these gains indicate some degree of natural or assisted recovery, their spatial extent and magnitude were insufficient to offset total biomass losses across the landscape.

Figure 2. LULC Classes of 2017, 2024, and LULC Transition Maps in SLRF

Carbon Emissions and Removals

Carbon accounting results consistently identify forest-to-non-forest transitions as the principal source of emissions. Conversion of forest to flooded vegetation and rangeland accounted for the majority of carbon losses, due to large differences in above-ground biomass between these classes. In contrast, carbon removals were dominated by rangeland-to-forest transitions, with comparatively small contributions from other land-cover changes.

Overall, the balance of emissions and removals indicates a net decline in forest carbon stocks over the study period. This finding aligns with broader regional and national trends, highlighting the vulnerability of even legally protected forests to gradual degradation and carbon loss.

Drivers of Forest Change: A Critical Review

Socioeconomic Drivers: Insights from SLRF

Across the reviewed literature, socioeconomic pressures are consistently identified as the primary drivers of land-use and land-cover (LULC) change in Myanmar's forest landscapes (Hansen et al., 2013; Woods, 2019; Naing Tun et al., 2021). These dynamics are clearly reflected in the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest (SLRF) in the Bago Region, where agricultural expansion, settlement growth, and dependence on forest resources for livelihoods have contributed to progressive forest degradation rather than abrupt large-scale deforestation.

Satellite-based analyses of SLRF indicate that forest loss and degradation are spatially concentrated along forest margins, access corridors, and areas adjacent to settlements, consistent with national and regional trends (Zewdie & Csaplovics, 2014; Pham et al., 2020). Incremental transitions from forest to rangeland, cropland, and periodically flooded vegetation suggest sustained smallholder-driven land-use change linked to subsistence agriculture, fuelwood collection, and local construction needs (Kyaw, 2018). These patterns reinforce the broader finding that forest carbon loss in Myanmar is closely tied to rural development trajectories and livelihood strategies rather than industrial-scale clearance alone.

Environmental and Climatic Influences in the Shwe Luang Landscape

Environmental and climatic factors further shape LULC dynamics within SLRF by interacting with human land-use pressures. The forest lies within a monsoon-influenced hydroclimatic regime, where seasonal rainfall variability and flooding strongly influence vegetation distribution and land suitability (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014; Leung et al., 2024). Sentinel-2-based classifications in SLRF show recurrent expansion and contraction of flooded vegetation in low-lying areas, reflecting interannual variability in rainfall and riverine flooding.

Periods of reduced precipitation increase vulnerability to forest degradation through moisture stress and reduced regeneration capacity, particularly in already disturbed forest patches (IPCC, 2022). Conversely, flood-prone zones tend to constrain permanent agricultural conversion but may still experience forest degradation due to altered hydrological conditions. Topographic variation within SLRF further modulates these responses, with upland areas exhibiting higher susceptibility to drying and gradual degradation during prolonged dry periods (Hunka et al., 2024). These findings illustrate how climate variability amplifies existing socioeconomic pressures, influencing both the spatial pattern and intensity of forest change.

Governance and Policy Constraints in Protected Forest Management

Despite its formal designation as a reserved forest, SLRF exhibits land-cover changes indicative of weak enforcement and governance constraints, a pattern widely reported for protected areas across Myanmar (Woods, 2019; Angelsen et al., 2018). Unclear land tenure arrangements, limited enforcement capacity, and overlapping institutional mandates reduce the effectiveness of forest protection on the ground. As a

result, illegal logging, small-scale encroachment, and unregulated land conversion persist despite existing policy frameworks.

Reviews of REDD+ readiness in Myanmar emphasize that without secure tenure, community participation, and effective benefit-sharing mechanisms, forest-dependent communities have limited incentives to support long-term conservation (Angelsen et al., 2018; Naing Tun et al., 2021). In the context of SLRF, these governance challenges help explain the observed disconnect between protected-area status and ongoing forest degradation detected through remote sensing.

Implications for Forest Monitoring, REDD+, and Climate Policy: Lessons from SLRF

The synthesis of evidence from SLRF demonstrates how high-resolution remote sensing-based LULC analysis, when integrated with IPCC Tier-1 carbon accounting, provides a robust framework for linking drivers of forest change to carbon outcomes (IPCC, 2006; Hunka et al., 2024). In SLRF, observed transitions from forest to non-forest classes are directly associated with carbon emissions, while areas of forest regeneration contribute to carbon removals, highlighting the dual role of degradation and recovery processes.

These insights are directly relevant to REDD+ monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV), as they enable spatially explicit identification of emission hotspots and restoration opportunities (Angelsen et al., 2018). However, the SLRF example also underscores that technical monitoring alone is insufficient; meaningful climate mitigation outcomes depend on parallel improvements in governance, tenure security, and community engagement.

Conceptual Framework Linking Drivers, LULC Change, and Forest Carbon Outcomes

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework Linking Drivers of Forest Change, LULC Dynamics, and Forest Carbon Outcomes in Shwe Laung Reserved Forest, Myanmar

Conceptual framework illustrating the interactions between socioeconomic, environmental, and governance drivers of forest change and their effects on land-use and land-cover (LULC) transitions and forest carbon outcomes, using the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest as a synthesis example. Socioeconomic pressures (e.g., agricultural expansion, settlement growth, and resource dependence), environmental and climatic variability (e.g., rainfall seasonality, flooding, and topography), and governance constraints (e.g., land tenure insecurity and weak enforcement) collectively influence observed LULC transitions detected using Sentinel-2 Level-2A imagery. These transitions drive forest carbon emissions and removals estimated using the IPCC Tier-1 stock-difference approach. The framework highlights how satellite-based monitoring links underlying drivers to policy-relevant outcomes, informing REDD+ monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV), climate mitigation strategies, and sustainable forest management interventions.

Conclusion

This review synthesizes recent advances in remote sensing-based land-use and land-cover (LULC) classification and forest carbon assessment, with a particular focus on their application in Myanmar's forest landscapes. The growing availability of high-resolution, freely accessible satellite data, especially Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance imagery, has substantially improved the capacity to detect forest change, capture subtle degradation pathways, and monitor regeneration processes in heterogeneous tropical environments. When combined with standardized carbon accounting frameworks such as the IPCC Tier-1 approach, these methods provide a transparent and scalable means of linking observed LULC transitions to forest carbon emissions and removals.

The reviewed evidence demonstrates that forest change in Myanmar is driven by a complex interplay of socioeconomic pressures, environmental and climatic variability, and governance constraints. Incremental degradation associated with smallholder agriculture, settlement expansion, and resource dependence often outweighs large-scale deforestation, highlighting the importance of monitoring fine-scale transitions that are detectable using Sentinel-2 imagery. Environmental factors, including monsoon-driven rainfall variability and flooding regimes, further shape spatial and temporal patterns of forest change, while weak enforcement and unclear tenure arrangements limit the effectiveness of existing protection frameworks.

The synthesis example of the Shwe Laung Reserved Forest illustrates how remote sensing can bridge the gap between environmental monitoring and policy-relevant decision-making. However, the review also underscores that technical advances alone are insufficient to halt forest degradation or achieve durable climate-mitigation outcomes. Effective forest governance requires the integration of robust monitoring systems with institutional strengthening, community engagement, and coherent land-use policies.

Recommendations and Future Directions

Based on the reviewed literature, several priority areas emerge for advancing forest monitoring and climate-informed land-use governance in Myanmar and comparable data-limited contexts.

First, national forest monitoring systems should institutionalize the use of high-resolution Sentinel-2 imagery for routine LULC assessment, with particular emphasis on detecting forest degradation and regeneration in addition to deforestation. Integrating these datasets into regular reporting cycles would enhance the consistency and transparency of forest change assessments.

Second, carbon accounting approaches should progressively move beyond Tier-1 where feasible, through the incorporation of locally derived biomass data and field measurements. While Tier-1 methods remain appropriate for large-area and initial assessments, targeted investments in forest inventories would reduce uncertainty and strengthen REDD+ reporting credibility.

Third, linking remote sensing outputs to governance and planning processes is essential. Spatially explicit identification of deforestation and degradation hotspots should directly inform enforcement strategies, restoration planning, and land-use zoning decisions, particularly at forest–settlement interfaces.

Fourth, strengthening land tenure clarity and community participation is critical for translating monitoring results into sustained conservation outcomes. REDD+ and related climate initiatives should prioritize inclusive governance structures that align local livelihood incentives with forest protection goals.

Finally, future research should focus on integrating remote sensing with socio-ecological data, including demographic, economic, and institutional variables, to better understand the causal pathways driving forest change. Such interdisciplinary approaches will be crucial for designing effective, climate-smart forest management strategies that balance conservation, development, and carbon mitigation objectives.

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Appendix

Table 2. SLRI-LULC Changes Transition Matrix for 2017 to 2024 (area in ha)

FID_Shwe_L	gridcode	Class_2017	Area_ha	FID_Shwe_1	gridcode_1	Class_2024	Area_ha_1	Change	Change_ha
0	1	Water	453.1580	0	1	Water	82.42680	Water - Water	48.23040
0	1	Water	453.1580	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Water - Trees	0.0989380
0	1	Water	453.1580	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Water - Flooded Vegetation	404.2460
0	1	Water	453.1580	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Water - Crops	0.1571410
0	1	Water	453.1580	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Water - Rangeland	0.1586290
1	2	Trees	18314.20	0	1	Water	82.42680	Trees - Water	5.531480
1	2	Trees	18314.20	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Trees - Trees	17081.10
1	2	Trees	18314.20	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Trees - Flooded Vegetation	866.1490
1	2	Trees	18314.20	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Trees - Crops	1.765970
1	2	Trees	18314.20	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Trees - Rangeland	356.6130
2	4	Flooded Vegetation	1286.410	0	1	Water	82.42680	Flooded Vegetation - Water	1.068540
2	4	Flooded Vegetation	1286.410	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Flooded Vegetation - Trees	0.4940060
2	4	Flooded Vegetation	1286.410	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Flooded Vegetation - Flooded Vegetation	1284.450
3	5	Crops	44.21180	0	1	Water	82.42680	Crops - Water	0.1152440
3	5	Crops	44.21180	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Crops - Trees	4.223070
3	5	Crops	44.21180	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Crops - Crops	30.8290
3	5	Crops	44.21180	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Crops - Rangeland	8.957980
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	0	1	Water	82.42680	Bare ground - Water	0.784660
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Bare ground - Trees	2.121060
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Bare ground - Flooded Vegetation	26.08180
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Bare ground - Crops	0.4346410
4	8	Bare ground	32.17480	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Bare ground - Rangeland	2.732130
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	0	1	Water	82.42680	Rangeland - Water	26.63890
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	1	2	Trees	17674.60	Rangeland - Trees	583.7170

5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	2	4	Flooded Vegetation	3353.390	Rangeland - Flooded Vegetation	771.1320
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	3	5	Crops	40.27720	Rangeland - Crops	7.041570
5	11	Rangeland	1696.010	4	11	Rangeland	675.6650	Rangeland - Rangeland	306.7110

